

Angelo Leogrande^{1*°}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Net inflows of foreign direct investment (FDI) as a percentage of GDP globally

Have grown by 109.82% between 2013 and 2020

FDI comprises net inflows of investments aimed at acquiring a lasting managerial interest (10% or more of voting stock) in a business operating in an economy different from that of the investor. It represents the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, other long-term capital, and short-term capital as recorded in the balance of payments. This series shows net inflows (new investment inflows minus disinvestment) into the reporting economy from foreign investors and is divided by GDP.

Net inflows of FDI as a percentage of global GDP in 2020. Cyprus, with a remarkable 100% of GDP represented by FDI inflows, tops the list. This exceptionally high figure can be attributed to the country's favorable tax policy, attracting investors with significant tax advantages. Cyprus has positioned itself as a hub for financial and real estate investments, thanks to its strategic location between Europe, Asia, and Africa. Hong Kong SAR, China (93.5%) and Singapore (87.6%) closely follow, underscoring their importance as global financial centers. Both countries offer a favorable business environment with advanced infrastructure, political stability, and transparent regulations. These elements make Hong Kong and Singapore attractive destinations for foreign investments, facilitating access to Asian markets. Malta (91.4%) and Luxembourg (76.4%) are other examples of small states that, thanks to advantageous tax policies and flexible regulations, manage to attract significant foreign capital flows. These countries offer incentives for multinationals and have created a regulatory framework that favors capital attraction. Mozambique (84.8%) and Ghana (69.3%), both developing countries, show significant FDI figures relative to GDP. These inflows are crucial for their economies as they represent sources of external funding that can be used for infrastructure development, job creation, and general welfare improvement. The attraction of FDI in these countries often concerns sectors like mining, agriculture, and energy. Ireland (84.5%) continues to be a prime destination for FDI due to its skilled workforce, presence of technological and pharmaceutical multinationals, and favorable regulatory environment. Irish tax policies have attracted technology giants like Google and Apple, making the country a central node for innovation and technology in Europe. In countries like Albania (72.9%), Serbia (71.2%), and Montenegro (73.3%), FDI represents a significant portion of GDP, highlighting their vital role in economic development. These countries have implemented economic reforms to improve the business environment, thus attracting foreign capital in sectors like infrastructure, energy, and tourism. The presence of the United Kingdom (70%) and the Netherlands (69.2%) among the main FDI recipients indicates their mature and diversified economies. These countries offer a stable and regulated environment, attracting investments in various sectors, including finance, technology, and services. Brexit, despite initial uncertainties, has not significantly diminished the attractiveness of the UK for foreign investors. Rapidly developing countries like Vietnam (70.4%) and Myanmar (67.7%) show significant FDI inflows, driven by economic openness policies and the relocation of manufacturing from higher labor cost countries. These investments are crucial for economic transformation and integration into global markets. Data analysis for countries like Brazil (67%), Colombia (67.6%), and Mexico (65.8%) shows that Latin America continues to be an attractive region for investors, thanks to abundant natural resources and

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

growing markets. However, political instability and economic uncertainties can negatively affect the region's attractiveness. Developed economies like Australia (66.9%), Switzerland (66.8%), Canada (64.4%), and Germany (64.4%) show FDI inflows that, while not at the levels of some small states, reflect solid confidence in their stable economic environments and advanced infrastructures. These countries offer secure and regulated markets, ideal for long-term investments. Emerging and diversified economies like India (63.4%), Indonesia (63%), and Nigeria (61.9%) demonstrate good levels of FDI attraction. These inflows are essential for supporting rapid economic development and addressing population growth and urbanization challenges. Finally, countries like Japan (61.4%) and South Korea (62.1%) maintain a steady flow of FDI thanks to their advanced and technologically sophisticated economies. Despite their strong domestic economies, they continue to attract foreign investments in sectors like technology, advanced manufacturing, and R&D.

Net inflows of FDI as a percentage of global GDP between 2013 and 2020. The data analysis on FDI as a percentage of GDP for various countries between 2013 and 2020 highlights significant changes, reflecting different economic, political, and social factors influencing the ability to attract foreign capital. Finland, for example, saw an impressive increase of 1977% in its FDI inflows relative to GDP, rising from 3.1% in 2013 to 64.4% in 2020. This extraordinary increase can be attributed to successful economic and political reforms that improved the business environment and attracted foreign investors. Finland's transformation into a technological and innovative hub has undoubtedly played a crucial role in this change. Another notable case is Yemen, which recorded a 1546% increase in FDI inflows as a percentage of GDP. This increase, though significant, may be more complex to interpret given the country's unstable political situation. Foreign capital inflows could be due to investments targeting specific sectors, such as natural resources, which remain attractive despite political difficulties. Egypt and Switzerland have also shown significant increases, with variations of 453% and 406%, respectively. In Egypt, this may be due to economic policies aimed at stabilizing the economy and making the country more attractive to foreign investors, especially in sectors like tourism and energy. Switzerland, already known for its economic and financial stability, has further consolidated its position as an attractive destination for foreign investments. Several African countries, such as Burkina Faso (392%) and Niger (389%), have shown considerable increases. These data reflect growing investor confidence in emerging African economies, often rich in natural resources and with significant economic growth potential. Similarly, the increase in FDI in countries like Tajikistan (386%) and Qatar (382%) indicates a strengthening of their economies through strategic investments in infrastructure and natural resources. In Asia, Japan has seen a 383% increase, highlighting the success of economic policies aimed at stimulating growth and innovation. Countries like Kuwait (342%) and South Korea (325%) have shown similar increases, indicating growing attractiveness for foreign investments due to favorable policies and a skilled workforce. The situation in the UK (293%) and the Netherlands (246%) indicates mature economies that continue to attract significant foreign capital flows despite political challenges like Brexit. These countries offer advanced infrastructure, political stability, and a favorable regulatory environment, which remain key elements for foreign investors. In Latin America, countries like Brazil (164%), Colombia (122%), and Mexico (221%) show significant increases, reflecting greater investor interest in these emerging economies. These countries offer opportunities in various sectors, including energy, agriculture, and technology, attracted by economic reforms and long-term growth potential. European countries like Italy (243%), Germany (268%), and France (218%) have seen moderate but significant increases, demonstrating the continued attractiveness of these developed economies. Fiscal policies and economic reforms have helped create a favorable investment environment, although global economic challenges have imposed some caution among investors. A particularly interesting case is Cyprus, which saw a 213% increase, consolidating its position as a hub for foreign investments thanks to advantageous tax policies and a flexible regulatory environment. Similarly, countries like Ireland (135%) and Luxembourg (76%) continue to be attractive destinations for investors, thanks to their favorable tax policies and economic stability. On the other hand, some countries have recorded

decreases in FDI inflows as a percentage of GDP. Hong Kong SAR, China saw a 7% reduction, while Singapore registered a 12% decrease. These declines can be attributed to global economic and political factors, as well as changes in regional dynamics affecting capital flows. The cases of Belgium and Mongolia, which saw decreases of 45% and 47%, respectively, are particularly relevant. These declines can be attributed to various factors, including changes in economic policies, political or economic instability, and increasing competition from other investment destinations.

Conclusions. The average net inflow of FDI as a percentage of GDP in the analyzed countries grew by 109.82% between 2013 and 2020, rising from 31.62 units to 66.36%. Some countries saw significant growth in net FDI inflows between 2013 and 2020, such as Finland with a value of +1977%, Yemen with +1546%, Egypt with +453%, Switzerland with +406%, and Burkina Faso with +392%. However, some countries experienced decreases in net FDI inflows relative to the period average, including Niger with -14%, Guinea with -18%, Luxembourg with -24%, Belgium with -45%, and Mongolia with -47%.

Source: <https://databank.worldbank.org/metadataglossary/world-development-indicators/series/BX.KLT.DINV.WD.GD.ZS>

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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